

There are three species of bear native to North America. Most numerous North American bears. The commonest is the American black bear, adopted by the brown bear after which the polar bear. Discovered throughout Canada, the USA, and Mexico. Weighs 200 to 600 pounds. Can be dark or gentle brown (cinnamon), sometimes even white. Not at all times black in colour. 900,000 and not threatened. □□Location: The American black bear may be found all through Canada, the USA, and Mexico. Nevertheless, some subspecies such because the Louisiana black bear are protected below the U.S. □□ Measurement: Adults weigh 200 to 600 pounds and are 5 to six feet in size. □□ Features: Most black bears are black, however their fur can vary from darkish brown to lighter brown (cinnamon) and even white on rare occasions. They have pointed ears and a straight face. Of all the bear species black bears are some of the very best at climbing trees. Their comparatively smaller measurement and shorter claws make them quick and nimble to climb timber for safety, meals, and even hibernation. The vast majority of their eating regimen is vegetarian consisting of berries, plant shoots, and nuts. □□ Weight loss program: Their diversified weight-reduction plan gives them the ability to dwell in a big range of habitats. Additionally they eat insects, fish, and carrion. □□ Harmful? They are the most likely bear to be encountered within the backcountry. And sure, they love honey. The grizzly and Kodiak are the 2 subspecies of brown bears in North America. Most widespread bear species are discovered within the northern Rocky Mountains, Alaska, Asia, Europe, and the Middle East. Brown bears are the most widespread of all bear species, discovered within the northern Rocky Mountains, Alaska, Asia, Europe, and the Middle East. Grizzlies are accountable for nearly all bear assaults in North America, with 46 per 12 months. Though their conservation status is "least concern", their unfold-out nature and reduced habitat make lots of the small remaining pockets fragile. The 200,000 brown bears of the world occupy a large number of habitats spanning deserts, forests, and mountains. All brown bears share a large build, a dish-shaped face, and a shoulder hump. Their hair is lighter at the ideas, which led to the identify of essentially the most well-known subspecies, grizzly. Brown bears forage on roots, berries, insects, and fish, and a few even hunt younger mammals reminiscent of elk and moose. Their colour varies from mild blonde to dark brown. The two subspecies in North America are the grizzly and Kodiak. □□Location: Grizzly bears are found within the northern USA, Canada, and Alaska. □□ Measurement: Adults weigh four hundred to 790 pounds, are 6.5 toes long, and have a shoulder height of 3. Three toes. □□ Eating regimen: Grizzlies eat berries, nuts, salmon and have been identified to prey on massive mammals. Coastal grizzlies are usually larger than these discovered within the Rocky Mountains resulting from a richer diet. Each year there are 46 attacks and 6 deaths. □□ Harmful? Known for his or her aggressive habits, grizzlies are responsible for probably the most bear assaults in North America. □□Location: Kodiak bears are only discovered on the Kodiak Islands, an archipelago in southwestern Alaska. □□ Measurement: Kodiak bears are almost as giant as polar bears, weighing 600 to 1,400 pounds, eight toes long, and four toes tall at the shoulder. □□ Weight-reduction plan: Their eating regimen is much like mainland grizzly bears. However, because of extra plentiful food sources, the islands can help a denser bear inhabitants. Geographic isolation from the mainland allowed the 3,500 Kodiak bears to become their very own subspecies. This has led to a extra advanced social construction which results in much less battle between bears. □□ Dangerous? Like grizzlies, Kodiak bears can be aggressive. Due to their isolation, there is only one assault on people every different yr. Largest species of bear on the earth weighing between 800 and 1,300 pounds. Weight loss plan is mostly made up of meat, often from seals. □□Location: Polar bears are the largest bears and largest land carnivores on the planet. Fur appears white but is definitely clear. The world's 20,000 to 30,000 polar bears range in the snow-lined arctic ice in Alaska, Canada, Russia, and Norway. □□ Size: Adult polar bears are 800 to 1,300 pounds and will be 7 to 10 toes tall. They are a threatened species resulting from lack of habitat from climate change. Regardless of their monumental dimension polar bears might be quick, maintaining a 6 mph pace within the water. □□ Options: Compared to other bears, polar bears have a slimmer body, slender head, longer neck, and paddle-like paws. For context, swimmer Michael Phelps gained Olympic gold medals with a 4.7 mph tempo! □□ Food plan: Their weight loss program consists principally of animals, particularly seals which they'll scent from a mile away. Though they seem white, their fur is actually clear and their pores and skin is black. □□ Dangerous? Polar bears might be extremely dangerous. They see humans as potential prey. Attacks are uncommon because of the remote nature of their habitat. Recognized for its cream color chest blazes. At 300 pounds one of many smaller bears. Easy to tame and infrequently common in circuses. □□Location: The Asian black bear is found in forests and shrublands across Asia from Iran to Japan. The inhabitants is estimated at 40,000 to 50,000 and is considered vulnerable. □□ Measurement: One of the smaller species, adults weigh round 300 pounds and stand 47 to seventy five inches tall. □□ Weight-reduction plan: Depending on the season it commonly feeds on small mammals, birds, fish, mollusks and carcasses or grasses,

fruits, berries, seeds, insects, and honey. Attacks on humans are growing as individuals encroach on their habitat. □□ Dangerous? They are one in all the easiest bears to tame (and therefore frequent in circuses), but Asian black bears are more aggressive than their North American counterparts. Found only in China. 99% of its eating regimen is bamboo. In reality, the second particular person in historical past to obtain a facial transplant was mauled by an Asian black bear while defending his sheep. Recognized for its iconic white face, eye patches, and striped body. □□ Location: Pandas are discovered solely in China. Only 1,500 to 2,000 stay within the wild and they are thought-about a susceptible species. □□ Dimension: Pandas weigh round 300 pounds and might be over four toes tall, an impressive feat considering they weigh solely about 3.5 ounces at start. It additionally has an in depth cousin, the Qinling panda which has the identical sample in gentle brown and white. □□ Eating regimen: Unlike other bears the panda's diet is homogeneous; 99% of what they eat is bamboo. □□ Options: The enormous panda is iconic for its white face, black eye patches, and striped body. All that fibrous bamboo keeps them common: they poop over 40 times a day! □□ Dangerous? Assaults are rare however dangerous, provided that pandas have one of the best bite forces of any carnivore. Smallest Bear weighing fifty five to 143 pounds. Found in South East Asia. 8 to 10-inch lengthy tongue for slurping up insects and honey. □□ Location: The Sun bear is found within the forest and shrubland of South East Asia and India. It's the least studied bear and. Its inhabitants is [cute panda teddy](#)

unsure however thought-about susceptible and on the decline as a result of loss of habitat and poaching. Sun bears are hunted for their gallbladders and different body components used in traditional medicines. □□ Size: They stand only 39 to 55 inches and weigh fifty five to 143 pounds making them the smallest bear. □□ Options: Solar bears have strongly curved claws, small rounded ears, and a brief snout. They are named for his or her pale, horseshoe-formed chest patch that looks like a rising solar. Additionally they eat seeds, fruit, birds, and deer. □□ Eating regimen: Solar bears tear apart bushes and nests to eat ants, bees, beetles, termites, and honey. Their love of honey has given them the nickname "honey bears." In truth, they've an extremely long tongue (8-10 inches) for slurping up insects and honey. Native to South Asia. □□ Dangerous? Due to its shy nature, attacks are rare. Lengthy, shaggy fur and mane gave them the identify sloth bear. Sloth bears are feared by rhinos and elephants. □□ Location: The Sloth bear is found within the low elevation savanna and shrubland of India, Nepal, and Sri Lanka. With a declining population of less than 20,000, they're thought-about weak. □□ Dimension: They're fifty five to 75 inches lengthy and weigh 200 to 300 pounds. □□ Options: With their lengthy shaggy fur and mane, they're simple to tell apart from different Asiatic bears. In actuality, they're very quick and can out-gallop people. European explorers mistook them for sloths after seeing them hanging upside down from bushes. They're noisy, messy eaters tearing up termite mounds with their big curved claws. □□ Diet: Their diet consists of termites, ants, and fruit. □□ Harmful? They are some of the aggressive bears, with the most assaults on people, largely attributable to surprise encounters. They blow the dust around with big puffs and suck the ants up so loudly they can be heard 600 toes away. Sloth bears stand their ground if threatened and do not combine well with rhinos and elephants, typically charging at one another when in proximity. Only South American bear. World's last quick-faced bear. The title "spectacled" comes from the lighter markings around their eyes that appear to be glasses. This susceptible species of 13,000 to 18,000 remaining bears are found in the cloud forests of the Andes from Argentina to Ecuador. □□ Size: They're mid-sized, weighing 175 to 275 pounds, and standing 47 to seventy nine inches tall. □□ Location: The spectacled bear is the world's last short-confronted bear and the one bear native to South America. □□ Options: The title "spectacled" comes from the lighter markings around their eyes that generally look like glasses. They spend most of their time in trees the place they construct nest platforms, sleep and jealously guard treasured fruit and carcasses. □□ Eating regimen: Spectacled bears are mostly herbivores with a diet consisting of principally cactus, bromeliad, palm hearts, and fruit, however they may opportunistically eat mammals like rabbits and tapirs. □□ Dangerous? Living in distant mountains, these shy bears could be the least harmful of all bear species. Their bodies are smaller than polar bears however larger than grizzlies. The Grolar bear (aka Pizzly) is a uncommon hybrid of a polar bear and a grizzly bear that occurs in each nature and captivity. Grolar bear behavior is closer to the polar bear. They function the lengthy necks of polar bears and the shoulder humps of grizzlies. In captivity, they've been documented stomping toys, similar to how polar bears break ice. Black-brown hybrid bears have been bred in captivity, notably at the London Zoo in 1859, but have not been confirmed within the wild. In 1986, a suspected grizzly-brown hybrid was shot however DNA checks were unable to find out what kind of bear it was. Adorable koalas are not bears, they're burly marsupials. Water bears aren't bears either, they are indestructible, microscopic animals that can survive in space. Most bear assaults happen when a bear is startled or protecting their cubs. Purple pandas? They're in their own family that are closer cousins

with skunks and raccoons than bears. 1. **BEWARE OF YOUR SURROUNDINGS.** Watch for bear scat and bear tracks that will indicate a bear is nearby, in which case you wish to be extra vigilant. Listed here are just a few ideas you can use to stop bear encounters and keep you and your hiking buddies protected. 2. **MAKE NOISE.** This helps bears know you're here so they don't by chance startle them. Consider attaching a bear bell to your pack. 3. **KEEP YOUR DISTANCE.** While you could have great intentions, a bear is likely to feel threatened when it sees you approaching and defend itself. 3. **Safe YOUR SCENTED Objects (AT CAMP).** If you happen to see a bear, don't try to method or feed it. This consists of meals, but additionally your toiletries, for example. Whichever method you select, make certain it is no less than 200 ft away from your tent so you don't appeal to bears to your campsite. 4. **Stay CALM.** In case you meet a bear, do not run. Try to make yourself look as large as attainable, waving your arms above your head. You may as well prolong a jacket above your head to make yourself look larger. Lock this stuff in a bear canister or use a bear bag to hang them up in a tree. Do not scream or try to scare the bear. 5. **USE BEAR SPRAY (AS A final RESORT).** Communicate to it calmly and slowly again away. Full instruction on how to make use of bear spray here. If the bear is dangerously shut (30 feet) or is charging at you, pull out your bear spray and use it in 1-2 second bursts, aiming slightly downward. 6. **Fight Back.** If all else fails and a bear assaults you, don't play lifeless. Which bear is the biggest? Averaging 900-1500 lbs, 8.Zero to 8.4 ft long, and 4.Zero to 5.25 feet tall, the biggest bear by each measurement and weight is the polar bear. The largest ever recorded was 2,200 lbs. Struggle back with all of your power and hope that it will back down. Which bear is essentially the most harmful? All bears are harmful if provoked. Globally, the Asian black bear is thought for the most attacks. When in bear nation, it's all the time sensible to hold bear spray. It's properly deserved, especially when cubs are round. Every year there are approximately forty six grizzly assaults, 6 leading to death. In North America, grizzly bears have the most fearsome repute. Which bear is the strongest? While you're most more likely to see an American black bear, on common there is just one attack per yr. By way of uncooked bite energy, measured in Newtons, the polar bear's chew reigns supreme. All bears are robust and to not be messed with. When utilizing the bite force quotient (chunk power relative to size), the solar bear packs probably the most punch. Initially named "Hotfoot Teddy", Smokey Bear was a black bear cub discovered in the spring of 1950 after a wildfire in New Mexico. He had climbed a tree to escape the hearth however sustained burns on his paws and hind legs. Quickly after he became an icon and to at the present time is the star of the longest-running public service announcement marketing campaign. Yogi Bear is an animated bear identified for his love of "pic-a-nic" baskets. Extra importantly Yogi Bear has impressed countless via-hikers to try to grasp the artwork of "yogi-ing", the act of not fairly begging however receiving favors from strangers. Baloo s a sloth bear, although he has some characteristics of the Asian black bear. He is an easygoing, pleasant bear who lives a responsibility-free life-style. He also is perhaps the primary bear to receive his pilot's license. Before he was the storybook teddy bear, Winnie the Pooh was a black bear from Canada which the author's son typically would go to on the London Zoo. Winnie is short for "Winnipeg," the city in Canada close to where he was from. Chris additionally wrote The way to Hike the Appalachian Trail. Equal elements backpacking meals and ultralight gear. After via-hiking the Appalachian Trail, Chris Cage created Greenbelly to provide quick, filling and balanced meals to backpackers. Get epic suggestions, guides and how-to's in your inbox every two weeks.

